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Research Article

**PREVALENCE OF LOW BACK PAIN AMONG
HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS****¹Dr. Maheen Ihsan, ²Dr. Saliha, ³Dr. Fatima Shanzey**¹ King Edward Medical University² Aziz Bhatti Shaheed Teaching Hospital Gujrat³ Yusra Medical and Dental College Islamabad**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Low back pain (LBP) has become the subject of an increasing amount of literature over the last 15 years. It is a common symptom in general practice. A total of 80 healthcare professionals including doctors, nurses, paramedical staff was included in this study. This cross-sectional study was conducted in King Edward Medical University. A predefined questionnaire was distributed. The mean age of the respondents was 25.25±2.34 years. There were 33 (41.25%) doctors, 25 (31.25%) nurses and 22 (27.5%) paramedical staff included in this study. According to the respondents, 37 (46.5%) suffered from low back ache occasionally and 43 (53.75%) suffered frequently. Almost every healthcare professional went through low back pain in their career and most of the them suffer from this very often. So, there is a need to formulate the policies leading to lower burden on the healthcare professionals.

Keywords: *Low back pain, healthcare professionals***Corresponding author:****Dr. Maheen Ihsan,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Pain has the capacity to cause suffering, alter lives and frustrate health care providers. Low back pain (LBP) has become the subject of an increasing amount of literature over the last 15 years. It is a common symptom in general practice (1). There is a common belief among many doctors that many cases of back-ache have a large psychological component and several studies have previously investigated the relationship between psychological factors and back pain (2, 3).

Low back pain (LBP) takes its place among the most common pain syndromes in the United States, Europe and Israel, and is a health problem of tremendous medical and socioeconomic dimensions. The National morbidity survey showed that back-ache accounts for about one third of the consultations for diseases of the musculo-skeletal system and connective tissue. Estimates from North America and parts of Europe predict that at any moment, 15-20% of the population suffers from LBP and that nearly all adults will experience some level of LBP during their lifetime (1, 3, 4).

Several recent studies and a U.S. National Academy of Sciences Institute of Medicine report suggest that outcomes in illnesses such as LBP may depend more upon doctor-patient interaction than on diagnostic and therapeutic techniques. For instance, reaching agreement with the patient on the diagnosis, or even just letting him or her feel understood, improves

outcomes. Awareness of patients' explanatory models of disease, the way individuals interpret an illness, may help to determine how they choose treatments, and has been shown in certain cases to help predict both compliance and results. However, little is known of patients' models, metaphors and lived experience of LBP (3, 5, 6).

The purpose of this study to see the prevalence of low back pain among the healthcare professionals. This study will help in formulating the policies leading to the strategies to adopt in order to reduce this low back pain.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A total of 80 healthcare professionals including doctors, nurses, paramedical staff was included in this study. This cross-sectional study was conducted in King Edward Medical University. A predefined questionnaire was distributed. All the collected data was entered and analyzed on SPSS Ver. 25.0. The qualitative variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

The mean age of the respondents was 25.25 ± 2.34 years. Mean age of the females was 24.54 ± 1.98 years and of males was 26.56 ± 0.89 years. There were 33 (41.25%) doctors, 25 (31.25%) nurses and 22 (27.5%) paramedical staff included in this study.

Average working hours of all the professionals was 6-7 hours daily. According to the respondents, 37 (46.5%) suffered from low back ache occasionally and 43 (53.75%) suffered frequently. Distribution of respondents according to the low back ache is given in the graph:

DISCUSSION:

Low back pain (LBP) is a major health problem in modern society. Seventy percent to 85% of the population will experience LBP at some time in their lives. Modern imaging techniques, such as computerized tomography and magnetic resonance imaging, provide much information concerning serious spinal pathology and nerve root compression. However, when these techniques are applied to common LBP they discriminate poorly between patients with back ache and normal subjects (1, 5, 7). Early blind laboratory screening is rarely useful. Medical history and clinical examination remain the main tools in the evaluation of common LBP. Each year, 5% to 10% of the workforce is off work because of their LBP, most of them for less than 7 days. Almost 90% of all patients with acute LBP get better quite rapidly, regardless of therapy. The remaining 10% are at risk of developing chronic pain and disability and account for more than 90% of social costs for back incapacity (8, 9).

CONCLUSION:

Almost every healthcare professional went through low back pain in their career and most of them suffer from this very often. So, there is a need to formulate the policies leading to lower burden on the healthcare professionals.

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